

Screening of rice genotypes for resistance to leafhopper, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée, and stem borer, *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker

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Leafhoppers (LF) and stem borers (SB) are destructive rice pests in Uttar Pradesh. LF and SB infestations occur in August and continue until crop maturity. The pests can be avoided by planting resistant varieties. We screened 30 aromatic rice genotypes for resistance to LF and SB in the field at CRS, Masodha, Faizabad, during 2001 and 2002 kharif. Each test entry was planted in 12 × 2-m

plots at 20 × 15-cm spacing with four replicates. All recommended crop management practices, except for plant protection measures, were followed. Infestation was recorded by counting the total number of leaves and the number of infested leaves (for LF) and the total number of tillers and damaged tillers (for SB) from 20 randomly selected hills of each genotype. NDR6175, NDR6093,

and NDR6232 were found to be resistant, 10 genotypes were moderately resistant, 15 were moderately susceptible, and two were susceptible to LF. Six genotypes were moderately resistant, 20 were moderately susceptible, and four were susceptible to SB (see table).

Reaction of rice genotypes to LF and SB 2001 and 2002 kharif.

Genotype	LF incidence (% infested leaves hill ⁻¹)				SB incidence (% infested tillers hill ⁻¹)			
	2001	2002	Mean	Reaction ^a	2001	2002	Mean	Reaction
NDR6175	6.25	0	3.1	R	3.3	0	1.6	MR
NDR6160	10.7	3.6	7.1	MR	4.3	5.2	4.7	MR
NDR6048	15.2	9.1	12.1	MS	9.9	8.0	8.9	MS
NDR637	16.1	9.7	12.9	MS	11.1	9.0	10.0	S
NDR637	-315.4	11.1	13.3	MS	4.3	11.9	8.1	MS
NDR6093	3.6	0	1.8	R	0	5.0	2.5	MR
NDR117	11.5	7.7	9.6	MR	8.7	10.1	9.4	MS
NDR6164	7.1	3.5	5.3	MR	7.1	8.5	7.8	MS
NDR6166	15.4	3.9	9.6	MR	6.5	9.1	7.8	MS
NDR6168	14.3	11.1	12.7	MS	5.4	9.1	7.3	MS
NDR6207	7.4	6.1	6.7	MR	3.7	7.1	5.4	MS
NDR6208	11.8	8.6	10.3	MS	8.8	8.8	8.8	MS
NDR6222	9.1	13.6	11.4	MS	9.1	4.6	6.8	MS
NDR6223	6.1	15.4	10.7	MS	3.0	0	1.5	MR
NDR6224	12.0	11.5	11.8	MS	11.5	7.7	9.6	MS
NDR6225	9.7	12.9	11.3	MS	9.6	9.6	9.6	MS
NDR6230	11.8	14.7	13.2	MS	8.1	7.2	7.6	MS
NDR6232	4.0	3.6	3.8	R	0	6.2	3.1	MR
NDR6233	4.6	9.1	6.9	MR	8.1	7.6	9.8	MS
NDR6237	8.7	8.7	8.7	MR	4.3	11.9	8.1	MS
NDR6239	14.3	10.7	12.5	MS	6.3	9.8	8.0	MS
NDR6234	8.0	4.0	6.0	MR	5.4	9.1	7.3	MS
NDR625	7.7	11.5	9.6	MR	8.1	7.9	8.0	MS
NDR6236	14.3	11.1	12.7	MS	11.9	8.8	10.3	S
Pusa Basmati	17.2	13.8	15.5	S	11.0	8.9	9.9	MS
T. Basmati	13.3	11.1	12.2	MS	10.5	1.1	10.8	S
T3	14.9	16.1	15.5	S	11.6	2.5	12.0	S
K. namak	10.7	7.7	9.2	MR	7.1	9.3	8.2	MS

^aMR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, R = resistant.